

BEST FISH CULTURE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCES TO ARARIA DISTRICT OF BIHAR

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Abstract

Araria is one of the new district created in Bihar has vast water resources for fish culture. The average fish production in the district is 1200 kg/ha/yr. Where as the potentiality is high. Keeping in view of high potential the present investigation was conducted to study the physico-chemical parameters of the soil and water and the present practices of fish culture prevailing in the district. On the basis of the findings recommendations has been made for best management practices for fish culture in the district.

Key words: *Physico chemical parameters, Aquaculture, Best practices for Aquaculture, Araria*

Introduction

The economy of Bihar is mainly dependent on agriculture, animal husbandry and fisheries. Fisheries and aquaculture sector play a key role in food security and employment generation as significant proportion of population depend upon fisheries, aquaculture and allied activities for their livelihood sustenance and income. Besides, the sector also generates precious revenue for the State. The importance of fisheries sector to the State economy has increased particularly after the creation of Jharkhand as a separate State. The State has two distinct land masses on either side of the holy River Ganga and is divided into 38 administrative districts, 21 in North Bihar and 17 in South Bihar. Bihar, lying in the heart of Gangetic plain, is blessed with fertile land resources though extreme hot and cold climatic conditions along with flood and drought situations are characteristic part of the geography.

The State is endowed with rich aquatic and fisheries resources in the form of rivers, flood plains, wetlands (chaurs), ox-bow lakes (mauns), reservoirs, tanks and ponds. The main culture fishery resources of Bihar lie in over 43,000 ponds and tanks of variable sizes covering a total area of about 65,000 ha distributed throughout the length and breadth of the State. Flood plains and other wetlands locally known as chaurs are other major fisheries resources and measure about 45,978 ha which are found mainly in the basins of Koshi-Gandak river systems of North Bihar. The Ox-bow lakes, locally known as mauns, are the discarded loops of meandering rivers which got cut off from the main rivers and is estimated to be about 9,000 ha. The 29 reservoirs in the State covering total water spread area of about 11000 ha is an important resource for fisheries development. Besides, 3200 km of rivers are the main resource for capture based fisheries in the State.

The annual fish production of the State, both from aquaculture and capture fisheries, has been estimated at 0.261 million tons against a demand of approximately 0.456 million tons. This has remained almost stagnant for many years (Ahmad 1996). Evidently, there exists a wide gap between demand and supply, to the tune of 43%, which is quite paradoxical in view of the vast fisheries resources in the State. The unmet demand is partly met from supply of fish from other States.

On one hand the State has huge underutilized and untapped fisheries resources which offers immense potential for fish production and scope for the development of rural livelihoods, while on the other, the state still depends for supply of about half of its demand of fish from other states. The very low average productivity in all culture based fisheries eco-systems, poor socio-economic condition of fishers and fish farmers, lack of adequate public and private investment and capital flow into fisheries sector, lack of awareness about aquaculture as a viable and profitable economic activity, non availability of adequate and professionally skilled human resource, ineffective and redundant services delivery systems, poor infrastructure facilities, etc have all been responsible for the limited growth and development of fisheries sector in Bihar. Thus there is an urgent need to bridge the gap between demand and supply of food fish. By effectively utilizing the water bodies and easily availability of the inputs.

Araria, which was earlier a sub-division of Purina, became a full-fledged district on January 14, 1990. There are two sub-divisions and nine Blocks in the district. Araria and Forbesganj are the two sub-divisions and Araria, Bhargama, Forbesganj, Kursakanta, Jokihat, Palasi, Raniganj, Narpatganj and Sikti are the nine Blocks. The district is located in the north-eastern part of the State under Agro Ecological Sub Region (ICAR) Eastern Plain, Hot Subhumid (moist) Eco-sub region (13.1), Agro-Climatic Zone (Planning Commission Middle Gangetic Plain Region (IV), Agro Climatic Zone (NARP) North East Alluvial Plain Zone (BI-2), Latitude 26° 8' 59", Longitude 87° 31' 11", Altitude 47 m above MSL and covers an area of 2,830 sq. kms. The boundary of the district on the north converges with the Indo-Nepal border. The geographical location of the district is important for security and other reasons. The district regularly suffers from natural calamity (flood). A number of rivers that criss-cross the district originate in Nepal and bring flood regularly during the rainy season. The district is primarily rural and agrarian. About 82.89 per cent of the population lives in the rural areas and a majority of them depend on agriculture for their livelihood.

Fish culture is an important source of animal protein and good digestibility which can play an important role in eradicating the malnutrition among the poor (Anon2006). The district has fisheries resources as ponds and rivers. The total ponds in the district is 2578 ha and total fish production from all the resources is 39200MT. The average fish production from pond is not different than the state average production, which is far below the national average production.

In the district the composite fish culture is the most common practice, Polyculture of indigenous and exotic carps is popularly known as Composite Fish Culture (CFC). It involves stocking and growing two or more compatible and complimentary fish species like Indian Major Carps (IMCs), Chinese Carps and the Common Carp in a water body like pond to maximize fish production by fullest utilization of all available niches in the pond ecosystem. The principle behind the CFC is to produce maximum quantity of fish per unit area from a scientifically managed water body by stocking fast growing, economically important, compatible species having shortest food chain utilizing the all ecological niches of the water body. Even though composite fish culture is an age-old practice in India but still there is wide gap in the production in research institution and even the neighboring state Andhra Pradesh.

The purpose of the present investigation is to study the prevailing fish culture practice in the district and technology available so that a better culture practices may be suggested for better utilization of the available resources. It will be useful for development agencies, Government organization and progressive farmers. It is important to have vertical development than the horizontal development to bring fish culture more remunerative and attracting.

In this work sample pond survey has been done to whole district to study the present status and ongoing fish culture practices so that a better technology could be suggested.

All the nine blocks of the district were surveyed through a pre tested questionnaire to study the status of fish culture technology adopted by the farmers. The soil and water sample were collected and analysed to study the physico-chemical parameters of soil and pond water.

Location of the District

Material and Methods

The survey was conducted in all the nine blocks of the district through pre tested questionaire. The soil and water analysis was done as per standard methods for Nutritional value of soil and physico- chemical parameters of the water (APHA 1971).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 : Nutrient status of the fish pond soil

Sl.no	Parameters	Observation
1	pH	7.1
2	Nitrogen (mg/kg)	5.20
3	Phosphorus (mg/kg)	14.9
4	Potash (mg/kg)	3.51
5	Organic carbon%	1.179

Table 2 : Physic-chemical parameters of the pond

Sl.no	Parameters	Summer	Rainy	Winter
1	Temperature (⁰ c)	31.7±3.5	30.0±2.7	13.0±2.0
2	pH	7.8±1.0	7.5±1.0	7.2±2.0
3	Transparency(cm)	23±2.0	25±1.0	26±2.0
4	Dissolve oxygen (ppm)	5.4±0.7	5.8±1.0	5.5±1.0
5	Carbon dioxide(ppm)	20±2.0	16±2.0	18±2.0
6	Alkalinity(ppm)	120±5.0	140±12.0	118±2.0
7	Hardness (ppm)	180±20.0	228.0±20.0	140±15.0
8	Electrical conductivity	560±12.0	710±5.0	650±25.0
9	Total dissolve solids (ppm)	690±25.0	740±25.0	650±20.0
10	Biological oxygen demand(at 25 ⁰ c)	2.8±4.0	3.2±2.0	2.2±0.1
11	Plankton(ml)	0.2±0.1	0.3±0.2	0.3±0.1

Table 3 : Managemental Practices adopted by the farmers

Sl.no	Village /block											
		Bhargama	Forbesganj	Kursakanta	Narpatganj	Raniganj	Sikhty	Araria	Jokihat	Palasi	Average	
1	Literate farmer (%)	40	40	40	50	40	30	60	50	40	43.3	
2	Trained (%)	80	70	70	50	50	40	60	50	30	55.5	
3	Average pond size	0.44	0.33	0.36	0.32	0.29	0.34	0.23	0.19	0.33	0.31	
4	Perennial (%)	100	30	40	90	60	30	10	90	0	48.8	
6	Age of the pond	>15 yrs	100	30	80	30	100	80	80	40	100	71.3
		>10 yrs		70	20			10	10	60		18.8
		>5 yrs				70		10	10			10.0
7	Pond preparation before stocking (%)	50	30	60	50	60	60	50	80	50	57.7	
8	Removal of unwanted fish(%)	50	30	40	50	40	40	50	20	50	41.1	
9	Removal of unwanted plants (%)	50	30	60	50	40	40	50	20	50	43.3	
10	Ploughing of the pond (%)	50	30	40	50	40	40	50	20	50	41.1	
11	Application of organic manure (%)	50	30	60	50	40	40	50	80	50	50	
12	Application of manure before stocking (%)	50	30	60	50	40	40	50	80	50	50	
13	Use of lime (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	
14	Inorganic fertilizer (%)	70	70	40	60	40	60	40	60	40	53.3	
16	Stocking (%)	Spawn	30	10	30	10	30	10	30	10	30	21.1
		Fry	30	70	30	80	30	80	30	80	30	51.1
		Fingerlings	40	20	40	10	40	10	40	10	40	27.7

17	No. of species stocked	3 species	20	50	20	50	20	50	20	50	20	33.3
		>3 species	80	50	80	50	80	50	80	50	80	67.7
18	Seed treatment (%)		20	20	20	10	10	20	20	20	20	17.7
20	Feeding of the fish (%)		50	90	60	80	60	80	60	80	60	68.8
21	Source of feed (%)	Home made	100	80	100	90	100	90	100	100	100	95.5
		formulated		20		10		10				4.45
22	Total month of feeding (%)	Upton 6 months	100	90	100	90	100	90	100	100	100	96.6
		>6 months		10		10		10				3.4
23	Fish sampling for test (%)		90	80	100	100	90	70	50	60	40	75.5
24	Do you face disease (%)?		10	20	00	40	10	30	50	40	70	30
25	Source of information for treatment of disease	Department of Fisheries	40	70	40	40	40	70	20	50	10	42.2
		Fellow	50	20	0	10	10	0	30	10	60	21.2
		Others	10	10	60	50	50	30	50	40	30	36.6
26	Production	Kg/ton/Yr	1.6	3.4	0.9	1.1	1.3	0.9	0.4	0.8	0.5	1.2

Literacy of the farmer

Literacy is most important in adoption of the technology. It has been found that the literacy rate in fish farmers ranges from 30-70%.

Training in fish culture:

There are several organization pertaining training to the fish farmers i.e. Department of Fisheries, Govt. of Bihar, Non Government organization etc. The training duration varied from 2-8 days, some farmers have also visited neighboring state as exposure visit. The training and exposure visit has created awareness among farmer for fish culture techniques.

Pond Size

It is reported that the pond should be 0.2 ha for commercial fish farming. The average fish pond of the project area is 0.35 to 0.45 ha. The size of the fishpond should be 0.2 ha (Jhingran 1991) for commercial fish culture. The size of the pond in the target district is almost to the recommended size (0.31 ha)

Seasonality of the pond

The fish production depends upon the seasonality of the pond. The perennial pond provides more production. Out of 9 blocks of the district three blocks has more than 50% ponds are perennial pond, which has more production potential. To have better fish production the pond should be perennial so that the culture period could be increased. To covert the seasonal pond into perennial pond the desiltation of the old pond is needed.

Nature of the pond

Most of the ponds are old ponds having age more than 15 years may be constructed for flood water management in the area. The age of the pond also showed the development trend in fish culture. The construction of new ponds i.e. less than 10 & 5 years age shows the recent interest in fish culture ,similar observations has been made by Pekar

et.al. (2001)To obtain better fish production in the old pond it is important to remove the muck accumulated in the pond bottom because these muck may release obnoxious gases which may be harmful for the fishes. The accumulated muck in the pond bottom can be very well utilized in the agricultural field for growing horticulture(Jhingran 1992)

Preparation of the pond

In fish culture before stocking the pond , the pond preparation is necessary so that the natural food of the fishes are available in the pond . To develop the natural food of the fish the application of organic manure, inorganic fertilizers and lime application is important. In the project area more than 50% farmers prepare the pond before stocking the pond.

Pond preparation: Removal of weeds

Aquatic weeds are unwanted plants that grow within the water body and along the margins. They remove a large quantity of nutrients from the water, which otherwise would go into the production of planktonic growth. Even the poor fish crop that is produced in weed choked water is difficult to harvest. The fishes are subjected to stress due to dissolved oxygen depletion and wide fluctuation between the dissolved oxygen values of the day and night.

Decomposition of the dead aquatic weeds further creates the oxygen problem. Dense growth of the submerged weeds restricts fish movement and interferes with fishing operations. Filamentous algae often get entangled in the gills of the fish and suffocate them to death. Floating weeds such as water hyacinth, pistia, etc., very often cover the entire water surface cutting off light drastically, thus resulting in critical reduction in primary productivity of the pond, 50% farmers practicing the removal of the weeds from the fish ponds.

Pond Preparation: Ploughing the pond

In the undrainable ponds muck accumulation is a common problem especially high stocked manure pond to increase the fish production. It is important to remove the muck at regular intervals. It has been found that more the 50% of fish farmers plough the fish pond whenever the fish pond dries up.

Pond preparation: Use of organic manure

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms including fish in fresh, brackish and sea water under controlled conditions with some intervention in the rearing process to improve production .One such intervention is the farming of fish in ponds with production activities such as regular stocking, feeding, and protection of fish from predators. Pond fish farming is not only useful as a source of protein for man and livestock and income for farmers who grow them but a way for utilizing organic wastes, unused land and aquatic resources .The wastes produced by farmed aquatic animals usually support substantial phytoplankton blooms in production ponds without adding inorganic nutrients. But, organic fertilization has been used to improve pond productivity for the culture of several species. A wide variety of organic materials have been used to promote the growth of zooplankton and phytoplankton as well as other invertebrates and pond micro-organisms. The use of animal manure is very effective for stimulating the growth of aquatic plants and animals.

Organic fertilizers are primarily used to increase populations of aquatic invertebrates such as worms, crustaceans and insect larvae, as well as zooplankton. These organisms provide food for fish and other farmed aquatic animals.

Pond preparation: Use of inorganic fertilizers

Fertilization is frequently used in the management of fishing ponds. Inorganic fertilizers are formulated using various chemicals containing nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (N, P, K). These elements, especially phosphorus, stimulate the growth of microscopic plants called phytoplankton, which in turn, serve as food for microscopic animals. Nutrients are applied to increase pond productivity, that is, aquatic life. Majority of the farmers in the project area use Single super Phosphate (SSP) in the pond in solid form.

Pant *et al* (2013) found that farmer using 28kg N, 7Kg Phosphorus/ha/week are able to increase the fish production by triple.

Pond Stocking

Ponds are stocked with seed of appropriate size after acclimatizing them to the new habitat when it is ready after fertilization. Both size and density of fish are important to achieve high yields. Fingerlings of over 100 mm in size are recommended for stocking in grow-out culture ponds. Stocking of smaller size of fishes may result in higher mortalities and slow growth during the initial months. In intensive polyculture ponds, a size of 50-100 g is preferred for stocking to realize higher survival of over 90% and better growth. Generally, a density of 5,000 fingerlings is kept as a standard stocking rate per ha for carp polyculture for a production target of 3-5 t/ha/yr. Stocking densities of 8,000-10,000 fingerlings/ha has been used for production levels of 5-8 t/ha/yr. Higher targeted fish production levels of 10-15 t/ha/yr are achieved by resorting to stocking at a density of 15,000-25,000/ha. In carp polyculture, species ratio are maintained for minimizing the inter-specific and intra-specific competition for food available at various trophic levels and zones in a pond. Two or more species occupying different niches could be utilized in a pond for exploiting the food available at various zones. While a combination of six species *viz.*, catla, silver carp, rohu, grass carp, mrigal and common carp has been proved to be the ideal combination for carp culture in India, species combination largely are decided on seed availability and market demand. Of these catla and silver carp are surface feeders, rohu is a column feeder, grass carp is a macro-vegetation feeder, and mrigal and common carp are bottom feeders. A proportion of 30-40% surface feeders (Silver carp and Catla), 30-35% mid water feeders (Rohu and Grass carp) and 30-40% bottom feeders (Common carp and Mrigal) is commonly adopted depending on the productivity of the pond. It is observed that farmers of the project area also stocks spawn and fry in the composite fish culture pond which is generally not recommended, but it is in practice due to loess cost.

In Andhra Pradesh the stocking the fingerlings weighing 50-250g each stunted for 10-24 months are utilized for stocking the ponds (Jhingran 1991)

Number of Species stocking

It is found that stocking of more than three species in the pond is important to utilize all the available niches of the pond and available food matter in the pond. In composite fish culture six species stocking was recommended. Minimum three species should be stocked to have good production. It is found that 80% farmer's minimum stocked three species in their pond.

Source of information

The fish farmers use to consult the different sources to improve the fish production and while occurrence to disease or abnormal condition observation during the fish culture. It has been found that maximum farmers consult the officials of the fisheries department to solve their problem. It is a good indication and shows the awareness of farmers in fish culture.

Fish Production

The average fish production of district was found 1240 kg /ha/yr.

On the basis of above observation and available technology a recommendation could be made for the best management practice for the district.

Conclusion

Bihar has rich water resources in the form of Rivers, Reservoirs, Lakes, Ponds, Tanks Chours and Mans and lot of fish biodiversity. The fish is one of the important foods of the state especially the Koshi region which receives regular flood. the common practice of fish culture in the tank and ponds are composite fish culture in which more than three species of fishes are reared at a time so that all the niches of the pond and the food matter is

properly used. As per all India coordinated project of composite fish culture the fish production was 10 tons/ha/yr. in the neighboring state Andhra Pradesh the average production is 8-10 tons and some farmers are getting about 14 tons/ha/yr. the average fish production in the state is 2.2 ton./ha/yr.

The fish production mainly depends on the inputs applied and technology adopted. Keeping the above view in mind it was found there is wide gap in production and requirement of fish in the state. To fill up this gap the only way is to increase the fish production /ha i.e. vertical expansion of the fish production (Boyd 1979).

Araria is one of a backward district of the state but have very good water resources and average fish production is 1.2 ton/ha/yr. the present work was taken up with a aim to study the physic-chemical parameters of the soil and water and fish culture technology adopted by the farmers so that the gap could be identified and the best managerial practices could be suggested for the district to increase the fish production.

The present observation revealed that the soil parameters are within permissible range for fish culture, the pH is alkaline range which is very much suitable for fish culture (Banerjea et.al 1970) because the acidic pH does not releases the nutrient applied in the pond and get locked in the soil. The applied manure has direct correlation to the fish production. The organic carbon percentage was 1.17 so the pond falls under the productive category for fish culture(Banerjea et.al 1967). The physic-chemical parameters of the pond water revealed that temperature varied from 13-31 0c, pH 7.2 to 7.8 dissolved oxygen transparency 23 to 26 cm, dissolved oxygen 5.4 to 5.8 ppm, free carbon dioxide 16 to 20 ppm, alkalinity 118 to 140 ppm, hardness 140 to 228 ppm, electrical conductivity 560 to760 , total dissolve solids 650 to 740 ppm, biological oxygen demand 2.2 to 3.2 ppm and plankton concentration 0.2 to 0.3 ml/50 l of water , the findings put the fish pond under favourable condition for fish culture (Banerjea 1967, Banerjea et.al 2013).

The present productivity of the district is 1200kg/ha/yr the survey revealed that the production could be increased by proper management. The survey for technology adoption revealed fish farmers literacy 43.3%,trained 55.5%,average pond size 0.31ha,perennial pond 48% only 57 % farmers prepare the pond before stocking,41% farmers remove unwanted fishes and 43% removes the unwanted plants from the pond.41% farmers plough the pond 50% farmers use the manure and inorganic fertilizer in the pond. Twenty one percent farmers uses the spawn for stocking the grow out pond and 33 % farmers stock less than three fish variety in the pond.69% farmers feeds the fishes that of 95 from home made feed. In case of problem 42 % farmers take advice from the Department of fisheries and average fish production calculated was 1.2 ton/ha/yr

On the basis of the findings of the work the management practices suggested for the district is,

1. Plough the pond in summer and remove the muck from the old ponds. This muck can be used in agriculture field for the crops.

2. In the perennial pond which is undrainable before starting fish culture the weeds and unwanted fishes should be removed because the weeds and unwanted fishes compete for food and space to the economical fishes. For removal of the weeds the repeated netting is suggested. Some piscicides may be applied. The piscicides of plant origin should be promoted, which has no or less side effects after consumption. The following table may be referred for selection of piscicides (Kumar 1996,2000).
3. The pond should be well prepared before stocking the fish seed. The pond should be of plenty of plankton concentration before stocking. To have good plankton 20% of the manure and inorganic fertilizers should be added as basal dose. The rest quantity should be divided in equal parts for application in ten months. The fortnightly or weekly application of manure and inorganic fertilizer gives better result
4. In scientific fish culture always bigger fingerlings are recommended for stocking in the pond more survivability and growth. The farmers stocking spawn in the grow out pond should be discouraged and advance fingerlings or yearlings stocking should be promoted. It will not only reduce the fish seed requirement of the pond but also increase the production in less duration. It will be very much useful for the seasonal ponds.
5. Most of farmers use less than three varieties of fish in the pond. Farmers should be motivated to have six varieties of fish in the pond to utilize all the space and food available in the pond.
6. Besides the plenty of natural food in the pond the supplementary food is also needed to increase the fish growth. It is recommended that supplementary feed should be applied which contains minimum 20% protein the feed may be applied directly by spreading in water at least thrice a day or bag feeding may be promoted which reduces the wastage of the feed.
7. After two to three months of the stocking of the pond sample netting should be done for observation of any diseases occurrence and proper treatment should be followed as and required.
8. The fishes may be harvested partially depending upon the growth of the fish and again the pond should stock with same number of yearlings, it increase the total fish yield from the pond.
9. On the basis of the present work a calculation has been made for the inputs for ponds of the district keeping a target of 3tons/ha/yr and 5 tons/ha/yr.
10. If the recommendation of the present work is adopted by the farmers and extension officials the total fish production will be more than doubled and direct and indirect employment will be created.

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